

INVESTIGATION OF TRANSFER OF NATURALIZATION OF ATHLETES IN THE OLYMPIC GAMES ACCORDING TO SPORT SCIENCES STUDENTS

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Abstract:

In today's globalizing world, unlike others, only a few countries and industries have remained or have opted out of globalization. Globalization shows its effects in sports. The desire of the countries to be more successful in international sports competitions, making athletes of different nationalities their citizens and entering them to the competitions constituted the concept of naturalization of athletes. Whether the successes of the naturalized athletes are ethical or whether these athletes prevent the development of domestic athletes is constantly on the agenda. From this point of view, our research focuses on the perspectives of university students studying in sports sciences to naturalization of athletes. Total of 891 participants voluntarily participated in the study. The Cronbach's Alpha value of the scale, which was used to find out the opinions of the participants about transfer of allegiance of athletes, was found 0,79. Percentage, frequency, t-test and Anova test were used to evaluate the scale. As a result the participants say that; in the future sports infrastructure development must be support instead of naturalization of athletes and their transfer fee should be used for investment in national athletes' development. Successes of the naturalization of athletes are the loss of prestige for Turkey. In order to prevent this, sports infrastructure based education programs can be given more importance.

Keywords: transfer; allegiance; Olympic Games

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1. Introduction

1.1 A Historical View on the Fact of Naturalization of Athletes

It is regarded that the first sample of naturalization in sports competitions is Cretan Sodates. Sodates was born in Cretan and competed for the sake of Cretan and succeed; however, he was naturalized for Ephesus and he attended to the competitions for the sake of Ephesus. Also, it is stated that the Cretans who were not pleased with this situation denaturalized Sodates (Jansen, 2018, 2). Even if naturalization of athletes dates back ancient Greece, the real acceleration happened just after the World War II. It is required to express that it has disguised in a different fact since 1990s.

1.2 The System of Naturalization of Athletes in Ottoman Empire

The system of naturalization of athletes is not a system that the previous Islamic states had. In the time of Ottoman Empire, it started with Çelebi Mehmet and it was legalized in the reign of Murat II. Many benefits of the naturalization system will be stated (Bayraktar, Alayoğlu, 2018, 89). However, the content of the study is about naturalization of athletes so the information in this context will be expressed.

In the system of naturalization, with the aim of fulfil the needs of soldier and manager, some non-Muslim children with some features used to be naturalized to be utilized in government service. Smart, healthy and sturdy children ranging in age from 8 to 18 used to be supplied with education of high quality by bringing them to İstanbul. Afterwards they used to be assigned a duty according to their abilities (Demir, 2017, 20-22). Some similarities and differences are between the system of naturalization in Ottoman Empire and the understanding of naturalization of athletes nowadays. The races of the children to be naturalized were important. However, in the samples of naturalization of athletes, it is not significant. When we consider that the young athletes who are successful and promising are naturalized today, it can be stated that it is similar to the system in Ottoman Empire in this sense.

As a term, "naturalization" means "collecting, compiling and gathering". It is stated as the work of choosing and gathering the children who would be enrolled to the guild of janissaries to be raised as soldiers in its historical meaning (Turkish Language Society, Great Turkish Dictionary). Naturalized athletes are the athletes who are transferred from foreign countries, naturalized in the country which transfers the athlete and represent the country in national and international competitions (Altunsöz and Koçak, 2017).

1.3 Naturalized Athletes in Our Country

Turkey sent 103 athletes to the Olympics games in 2016 and 29 of them were naturalized athletes. To the Olympic Games (1984) which Turkey joined with naturalized athletes for the first time, 48 athletes were sent but one of them was naturalized athlete. This amount increasingly continued in the following years. In the Table 1, the number of the athletes joined the Olympic Games, the number of the

naturalized athletes and the number of the medals won by naturalized athletes is presented.

Table 1: The Number of the Athletes and Naturalized Athletes that Turkey Has Sent to the Olympic Games and the Number of the Medals Naturalized Athletes Won (<http://www.olimpiyatkomitesi.org.tr/Olimpiyat-Oyunlari-Detay/120/>)

The year of the Olympic Games	The number of the medals	The number of the athletes	The number of the naturalized athletes	Medals won by naturalized athletes
1936	1 Gold, 1 Bronze	60		
1948	6 Gold, 4 Silver, 2 Bronze Wrestling	48		
1952	2 Gold, 1 Bronze	60		
1956	3 Gold, 2 Silver, 2 Bronze	15		
1960	7 Gold, 2 Silver	55		
1964	2 Gold, 3 Silver, 1 Bronze	25		
1968	2 Gold	33		
1972	1 Silver	30		
1984	3 Bronze	48	1	
1988	1 Gold, 1 Silver	50	1	1
1992	2 Gold, 2 Silver, 2 Bronze	47	3	1
1996	4 Gold, 1 Silver, 1 Bronze	54	6	2
2000	3 Gold, 2 Bronze	59	9	1
2004	3 Gold, 3 Silver, 5 Bronze	66	4	
2008	1 Gold, 3 Silver, 3 Bronze	68	12	2
2012	1 Gold, 2 Silver, 1 Bronze	114	10	
2016	1 Gold, 3 Silver, 4 Bronze	103	29	2

2. The Method of the Study

2.1 Participants

On the purpose of clarifying positive and negative thoughts about naturalized athletes in the literature, the students' opinions who study in faculty of sport sciences were asked. By considering the answers to the questions formed with this aim, results were obtained. In the research, questionnaire form was used as data collecting tool of the quantitative research method. The sample of the research was composed of 891 individuals who study at school of physical education and sports/ faculty of sport sciences. Data was collected with the method of simple random sampling and the questionnaire was implemented on the students from nine universities. 11.6 % of the participants are from Atatürk University, 9.9% are from Selçuk University, 12.6% are

from Cumhuriyet University, 8.8% are from Adnan Menderes University, 11.3 % are from Muğla University, 11.7 % are from Celal Bayar University, 6.6 % are from İnönü University, 16.5 % Karadeniz Technical University and 11.1 % are from Uludağ University.

2.2 Data Collecting Tools

A. Demographic Information Form

In this form, to receive students' demographic information, some questions about their department, gender, level of sportsmanship, sports branch categories they are interested in or perform, being abroad and living abroad (three months at least).

B. The Scale Formed to get Students' Opinions about Naturalized Athletes

This scale was formed to get students' opinions about naturalized athletes who join the Olympic Games and comprised of 18 questions. The questions were determined with the authorities in the field and item pool with 20 items was formed. After the evaluations, the number of the questions of the scale prepared with 20 questions was reduced in 18 questions. With the scale pre- application was performed with 30 individuals. The answers were ranked with 3 points Likert scale (I agree, I am indecisive, I disagree). While statements notifying positive attitudes about naturalized athletes are in the first nine questions, statements of negative attitudes about naturalized athletes are presented in the last nine questions. Cronbach Alpha reliability coefficient of the scale was determined as 0,79. It could be stated that the questionnaire implemented on the students is reliable thanks to that result.

2.3 Statistical Analysis

In estimating the data, SPSS 21 statistical program was used. In comparing the variances, percent, frequency, t-test and ANOVA tests were used. Estimating the data was done over the participants' total score of their answers for each question. In this research the level of statistical significance was regarded as $p < 0.5$.

3. Findings

Table 2: Demographic Information

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent
Department	Coaching	236	26,5	26,5
	Teaching	238	26,7	26,7
	Sports Management	223	25,0	25,0
	Recreation	194	21,8	21,8
Gender	Female	351	39,4	39,4
	Male	540	60,6	60,6
The Level of Sportsmanship	National Athlete	154	17,3	17,3
	Certified Club Athlete	439	49,3	49,3
	Athlete performing non- certified sports	298	33,4	33,4

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Sports Branch	Team Sports	510	57,2	57,2
	Individuals Sports	381	42,8	42,8
Being abroad	Yes	266	29,9	29,9
	No	625	70,1	70,1
Living Abroad Longer than Three Months	Yes	70	7,9	7,9
	No	821	92,1	92,1

Table 2 26.5 % of the participants are the students of coaching department, 26.7% of them are teaching students, 25 % of them are from sports management department, 21.8 % of them from recreation department. 17.3 % of them are national athletes, 49.3% of them certified club athletes, 33.4 % of them do not perform certified sports. 57.2% of the participants perform team sports, 42.8% of them perform individual sports. 29.9% of them have been abroad before, 70.1% of them have not been abroad. 7.9% of the participants have lived for longer than 3 months abroad.

Table 3: Point Average of the Participants' Answers to the Questions

Naturalized Athletes and the Olympic Games		I agree		I am indecisive		I disagree	
		N	%	N	%	N	%
1. Naturalized athlete application is a truth of sports of the World that's why the application of naturalized athlete should be supported in Turkey.	In Total						
	891	343	38,5	162	18,2	381	43,3
2. It is important for the international prestige of our country that naturalized athletes participate the Olympic Games and win medals for the sake of Turkey.	891	384	43,1	175	19,6	332	37,2
3. It was wealth for our country's sport that 29 athletes out of 103 athletes who attended 2016 Olympic games for the sake of Turkey are naturalized athletes.	891	299	33,6	166	18,6	426	47,8
4. It is a positive development for our country's sport that 3 medals out of 8 were won by naturalized athletes of Turkey in 2016 Rio Olympic Games.	891	308	34,5	174	19,5	409	46,0
5. Naturalized athletes' international successes are on duty of locomotive for Turkey to win Olympic medals in some sports branches.	891	335	37,6	230	25,8	326	36,5
6. In globalizing world, it does not matter anymore which countries athletes compete for the sake of in the Olympic Games.	891	320	35,6	179	20,1	395	44,3
7. In the Olympic Games, athletes should be allowed to compete for the sake of the countries they want.	891	282	31,6	172	19,3	437	49,0
8. Naturalizing the athletes who are taken winning medals for granted in the Olympic Games by spending great amount of money are not loss for	891	204	22,9	200	22,4	487	54,7

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Turkey.							
9. Turkey should naturalize the athletes with high potential who manage to win medals and have Olympic successes in the past.	891	289	32,5	177	19,9	425	47,7
10. The application of naturalization of athletes provides a basis for causing Turkey to fall behind.	891	427	48,0	200	22,4	264	29,6
11. If the money spent for naturalized athletes is spared for sports substructure in our country, Turkey could win more Olympic medals in the future.	891	584	65,5	145	16,3	162	18,2
12. Naturalized athletes should not be competed in the Olympic Games.	891	429	48,1	197	22,1	265	29,7
13. The application of naturalization of athletes is not ethical.	891	360	40,4	240	26,9	291	32,6
14. International Olympic Committee (IOC) should complicate the rules and judicial process of being naturalized athletes.	891	445	50,0	240	26,9	206	23,1
15. Emergent restrictions about the number of naturalized athletes in Turkey should be imposed.	891	470	52,8	189	21,2	232	26,0
16. The application of naturalization of athletes should be gradually renounced in Turkey.	891	462	51,8	221	24,8	208	23,3
17. Even if nationalized athletes win 10 medals for the sake of Turkey in 2020 Tokyo Olympics, this should not be regarded as a success.	891	440	49,4	183	20,5	268	30,1
18. The applications of naturalization of athletes have not compromised with recent nationalization politics of Turkey.	891	437	49,0	238	26,7	216	24,3

In Table 3, in the first question 38% of the participants' state that they agree, 43.3% of them disagree and 18.2% of them are indecisive. For the second question, 43.1% of them state that they agree, 19.6% of them are indecisive and 37.3% disagree. In the third question, 33.6% of them agree, 18.6% are indecisive and 47.8% of them disagree. For the fourth question, 34.6% of them agree, 19.5% are indecisive and 45.9% of them state that they totally disagree. In the fifth question, 37.6% of the participants agree, 25.8% of them are indecisive and 36.6% of them disagree. For the sixth question, 35.6% of them agree, 20.1% are indecisive and 44.3% of them state that they disagree. When we look at the seventh question, 31.6% of the participants agree, 19.3% of them are indecisive and 49% of them state that they disagree. For the eighth question, 22.9% of them agree, 22.4% of them are indecisive and 54.7% of them disagree. In the ninth question, 32.4% of them state that they agree, 19.9% of them are indecisive and 47.7% of them disagree. In the tenth question, 47.9% of the participants state that they agree, 22.4% of them are indecisive and 29.6% of them disagree. For the question 11, 65.5% of them agree, 16.3% are indecisive and 18.2% of them disagree. In the question 12, 48.1% of them state that they agree, 22.1% of them are indecisive and 29.7% of them disagree. In the question 13, 40.4% of them agree, 26.9% of them are indecisive and 32.7% of them disagree. For the question 14, 49.9% of them agree, 26.9% of them indecisive and 23.1% of them disagree. In the question 15, 52.7% of the participants state that they agree, 21.2% of them are

indecisive and 26% of them disagree. For the question 16, 51.9% of them agree, 24.8% of them are indecisive and 23.3% of them disagree. When we see the question 17, 49.4% of them agree, 24.5% of them are indecisive and 30.1% of them disagree. For the question 18, 49% of them agree, 26.7% of them are indecisive and 24.3% of them disagree.

Table 4: The Answers Given According to the Gender Variance

	Gender	N	X	Std. Deviation	P
If the money spent for naturalized athletes is spared for sports substructure in our country, Turkey could win more Olympic medals in the future.	Female	351	1,4558	,75036	,030
	Male	540	1,5722	,80142	

According to gender variance, statistically difference among the answers of the participants was just seen in the question 11. According to the answers given, female participants look more positively the question 'If the money spent for naturalized athletes is spared for sports substructure in our country, Turkey could win more Olympic medals in the future' than the male participants do.

Table 5: The State of Being Abroad (t-test)

	Answer	N	X	Std. Deviation	P
The application of naturalization of athletes provides a basis for causing Turkey to fall behind.	Yes	266	1,7105	,82579	,014
	No	625	1,8624	,87355	
If the money spent for naturalized athletes is spared for sports substructure in our country, Turkey could win more Olympic medals in the future.	Yes	266	1,3910	,68773	,000
	No	625	1,5840	,81437	
Naturalized athletes should not be competed in the Olympic games.	Yes	266	1,5602	,79036	,000
	No	625	1,8064	,86006	

In the participants' answers to the question of being abroad for at least three months, statistically significant differences were seen in the questions 10, 11, 15. To the questions of "The application of naturalization of athletes provides a basis for causing Turkey to fall behind, If the money spent for naturalized athletes is spared for sports substructure in our country, Turkey could win more Olympic medals in the future, Emergent restrictions about the number of naturalized athletes in Turkey should be imposed" the negative answer was found higher.

Table 6: The Answers Given According to the Variance of Department (Anova)

Department		N	Av.	SS	F (p)	Difference (LSD)
Naturalized athlete application is a truth of sports of the World that's why the application of naturalized athlete should be supported in Turkey.	Coaching ¹	236	2,1780	,87647	7,352 (,000)	3>1,2,4
	Teaching ²	238	2,1765	,91998		
	Sports Management ³	223	1,8610	,88198		
	Recreation ⁴	194	1,9485	,89756		
It is important for the international prestige of our country that	Coaching ¹	236	2,0042	,87761	3,125 (,025)	3>1,2,4
	Teaching ²	238	1,9748	,91828		

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naturalized athletes participate the Olympic games and win medals for the sake of Turkey.	Sports Management ³	223	1,7848	,89460		
	Recreation ⁴	194	2,0052	,87271		
It was wealth for our country's sport that 29 athletes out of 103 athletes who attended 2016 Olympic games for the sake of Turkey are naturalized athletes.	Coaching ¹	236	2,2415	,86844	5,682 (,001)	3>1,2,4 4>2
	Teaching ²	238	2,2479	,88679		
	Sports Management ³	223	1,9507	,89658		
	Recreation ⁴	194	2,1134	,88600		
It is a positive development for our country's sport that 3 medals out of 8 were won by naturalized athletes of Turkey in 2016 Rio Olympic games.	Coaching ¹	236	2,1864	,89394	4,668 (,003)	3>1, 2, 4 4>1,2
	Teaching ²	238	2,2101	,87027		
	Sports Management ³	223	1,9238	,89971		
	Recreation ⁴	194	2,1237	,87282		
Naturalizing the athletes who are taken winning medals for granted in the Olympic games by spending great amount of money is not a loss for Turkey.	Coaching ¹	236	2,4661	,76833	6,708 (,000)	3>1, 2
	Teaching ²	238	2,3908	,78127		
	Sports Management ³	223	2,2152	,83738		
	Recreation ⁴	194	2,1649	,87783		
The application of naturalization of athletes provides a basis for causing Turkey to fall behind.	Coaching ¹	236	1,7373	,86961	5,750 (,001)	2>1,3,4
	Teaching ²	238	1,7311	,84392		
	Sports Management ³	223	1,8027	,83104		
	Recreation ⁴	194	2,0361	,87790		
If the money spent for naturalized athletes is spared for sports substructure in our country, Turkey could win more Olympic medals in the future.	Coaching ¹	236	1,4534	,73943	11,648 (,000)	2>1,3,4
	Teaching ²	238	1,4034	,71535		
	Sports Management ³	223	1,4888	,75254		
	Recreation ⁴	194	1,8093	,88142		
Naturalized athletes should not be competed in the Olympic games.	Coaching ¹	236	1,6992	,82421	6,207 (,000)	2>3,4
	Teaching ²	238	1,7395	,85153		
	Sports Management ³	223	1,8341	,86175		
	Recreation ⁴	194	2,0309	,89273		
The application of naturalization of athletes is not ethical.	Coaching ¹	236	1,8559	,81763	3,022 (,000)	1>2,3,4
	Teaching ²	238	1,8950	,86754		
	Sports Management ³	223	1,8834	,86724		
	Recreation ⁴	194	2,0825	,84154		
International Olympic Committee (IOC) should complicate the rules and judicial process of being naturalized athletes.	Coaching ¹	236	1,6229	,75353	11,581 (,000)	1>2,3,4
	Teaching ²	238	1,6345	,79873		
	Sports Management ³	223	1,6951	,78633		
	Recreation ⁴	194	2,0258	,86039		
Emergent restrictions about the number of naturalized athletes in Turkey should be imposed.	Coaching ¹	236	1,6017	,82141	12,659 (,000)	1>2,3,4
	Teaching ²	238	1,6387	,82402		
	Sports Management ³	223	1,6951	,81998		
	Recreation ⁴	194	2,0515	,86223		
The application of naturalization of athletes should be gradually renounced in Turkey.	Coaching ¹	236	1,6102	,81511	6,944 (,000)	1>2,3,4
	Teaching ²	238	1,6092	,79730		
	Sports Management ³	223	1,7623	,81208		
	Recreation ⁴	194	1,9175	,82286		

As a result of one -way analysis of variance (ANOVA) implemented to determine the differences according to the departments towards the questions asked in order to receive the students' opinions about naturalized athletes, a significant difference among the questions 1, 2, 3, 4, 8, 10, 11, 12, 13, 14, 15 and 16 was seen. After Post- Hoc (LSD) analysis the students of sports management department have higher scores in the questions 1, 2, 3, 4 and 8 than the other departments. The students of teaching department have higher scores in the questions 10, 11, 12 than the other departments. In the questions 13, 14, 15, coaching department students have higher scores than the other students.

Table 7: The Answers about the Level of Sportsmanship

		N	Av.	SD	F (p)	Difference (LSD)
Naturalizing the athletes who are taken winning medals for granted in the Olympic games by spending great amount of money is not a loss for Turkey.	National athlete ¹	154	2,1948	,89353	5,191 (,006)	3>1,2
	Certified club athlete ²	439	2,1367	,89366		
	Athlete performing non-certified sports ³	298	2,1544	,86242		
The application of naturalization of athletes provides a basis for causing Turkey to fall behind.	National athlete ¹	154	1,7078	,83959	4,660 (,010)	1>2,3
	Certified club athlete ²	439	1,7745	,86626		
	Athlete performing non-certified sports ³	298	1,9362	,85633		
If the money spent for naturalized athletes is spared for sports substructure in our country, Turkey could win more Olympic medals in the future.	National athlete ¹	154	1,3312	,64732	9,041 (,000)	1>2,3
	Certified club athlete ²	439	1,5080	,76409		
	Athlete performing non-certified sports ³	298	1,6544	,85162		
The application of naturalization of athletes is not ethical.	National athlete ¹	154	1,8247	,83340	3,875 (,021)	1>2,3
	Certified club athlete ²	439	1,8838	,85083		
	Athlete performing non-certified sports ³	298	2,0302	,85424		
International Olympic Committee (IOC) should complicate the rules and judicial process of being naturalized athletes.	National athlete ¹	154	1,6299	,79172	8,649 (,000)	1>2,3
	Certified club athlete ²	439	1,6606	,77993		
	Athlete performing non-certified sports ³	298	1,8893	,84755		
Emergent restrictions about the number of naturalized athletes in Turkey should be imposed.	National athlete ¹	154	1,5390	,78493	12,285 (,000)	1>2,3
	Certified club athlete ²	439	1,6765	,83593		
	Athlete performing non-certified sports ³	298	1,9161	,86243		

As a result of one -way analysis of variance (ANOVA) implemented to determine the differences among their opinions about the level of sportsmanship towards the questions asked in order to receive the students' opinions about naturalized athletes, in the eighth question, only the ones who receive education of sports at schools have high

scores. In the questions 10, 11, 13, 14 and 15 national athletes think in a different way than the others.

4. Discussion and Result

In this chapter of the study foreign based athlete practice try to explain ethics, economic, moral and social aspects.

Reiche and Tinaz (2018) in their study said that naturalization of the athletes of Qatar and Turkey by inserting their success in international competitions, has stressed that the key to the success of the sports field. When the 2016 Olympic Games in particular Turkey has used both male and female foreign based athletes. In another study by Reiche (2015), the use of foreign based athletes shows that rich countries can become a global sports center from scratch. In a study conducted in Japan, which is a different culture, it was mentioned that after the recruitment of famous sports stars, they adopted local Japanese culture and became increasingly assimilated (Chiba et al., 2001).

In the study of Gorokhov and Yakovleva (2015), the perspective of foreign based athletes in Russia at the 2014 Sochi Winter Olympics was examined. According to the study, it was concluded that the bond between the spectator and the athlete did not weaken or impair the national pride of the sport and they emphasized that the bond between the spectator and the athlete was identified with the winner. Nadia Nadim who is Afghan origin plays for Danish women's national football team. In the period 2016-2017, the Danish press adopted the Danish identity and was constantly brought up. However, Nadim's attribution as Danish has damaged her origin and connection with her transnational sub-identities (Agergaard, 2017). Mesut Özil, another football player of different origins, said in an interview after he left the German national football team "*I am German when we win I am immigrant when we lose*" (http 1). This dilemma also supports by Carmi and Kidron (2018). They said that immigrant athletes can be unifying and can be excluded at the same time. Because of their ethnicity.

The inclusive and embracing diversity of sports is related to the extent to which sports organizations and the media can meet this diversity within the country. Sport and media have a major role to play in this process (Agergaard, 2017).

In accordance with the answers given by university students studying in the field of sports sciences, comments were made considering the average score of the questions.

In this direction, "Naturalized athlete application is a truth of sports of the World that's why the application of naturalized athlete should be supported in Turkey." item resulted disagree by participants more than average.

It is thought that the majority of the participants did not support naturalization of the athletes because of the desire of the athletes who will represent our country in international sports organizations to be native and the successes obtained by the foreign based athletes do not make sense.

Participants largely disagree with following items which are “In globalizing world, it does not matter anymore which countries athletes compete for the sake of in the Olympic games.”, “In the Olympic games, athletes should be allowed to compete for the sake of the countries they want” The globalizing aspect of sports is not generally accepted by the participants. It is thought that our country should use internal resources more effectively in training and competing athletes. The wrestling and gymnastics federation, which has shown a successful management approach in this way, has achieved great success with Turkish athletes recently.

Taking the athletes trained with money or from other countries and competing on behalf of our country may mean collapse of Turkish sports management Our country's manpower and facilities should be used in a more organized way to produce athlete training policies. Increase in the number of foreign based athletes may be related with the following factors in Turkey; lack of sporting culture, inability to train athletes and coaches due to lack of sports infrastructure, failures in international competitions or the ever-changing education system and sports policies (Altunsoz & Kocak, 2017). Therefore; it is wrong to form policies that will only bring success due to foreign based athletes. Action plans are required for the training of our own athletes with emphasis on sport infrastructure and the dissemination of sports culture is required.

Participants think positively about following items “The application of naturalization of athletes provides a basis for causing Turkey to fall behind” and “If the money spent for naturalized athletes is spared for sports substructure in our country, Turkey could win more Olympic medals in the future.” These thoughts are the most obvious indicator of negative perception on foreign based athletes and will not contribute to Turkey’s national teams.

Participants mostly agree with following items “International Olympic Committee (IOC) should complicate the rules and judicial process of being naturalized athletes”, “Emergent restrictions about the number of naturalized athletes in Turkey should be imposed.”, “The application of naturalization of athletes should be gradually renounced in Turkey.” These answers of items emphasized that the administrative decisions and policies of sports institutions and organizations related to foreign based athletes should be revised.

As a result of the study, some differences were found according to demographic characteristics. Male participants agree rate of “If the money spent for naturalized athletes is spared for sports substructure in our country, Turkey could win more Olympic medals in the future.” item higher than female participants. According to this answer male participants think that for to win more medals in Olympics need to invest in sporting infrastructure instead of foreign based athletes.

It can be said that the students of department of sports management think more positively about the foreign based athletes than the other students. The other departments are not satisfied with the achievements of the 2016 Rio Olympics. Similarly İmamoğlu, (2016), said that according to Turkey's population and economic level received medals and degrees at the Olympic Games in Rio are deemed inadequate.

Teaching, coaching and recreation department students think to participate foreign based athletes on behalf of Turkey to win medals at the Olympics and the opinion is not important in terms of international prestige of our country. İmamoğlu, (2016) also said that at the 2016 Rio Olympics, medals achieved by foreign athletes, affected Turkey's prestige negatively.

Gülhan (2016) says that no one will ever have the problem of raising athletes with the foreign based athlete method and that it is seen that raising athletes from the basic level to pro will be seen as luxury in time.

When we examine Duman et al. (2019)'s study we see that foreign based athletes win medals, but they have failed to introduce Turkey's promote recognition at international field.

The results of the assessments, despite the potential it has, Turkey failed to show the expected success in sports (Altun and Kocak, 2015). In particular, there are a record number of foreign based athletes at the 2016 Rio Olympic Games. Although the Turkish team nearly one third of foreign based athletes, Turkey, could not achieve the desired success at the Rio 2016 Summer Olympic Games (İmamoğlu, 2016). Referring to studies about the foreign based athletes in Turkey, there is a negative attitude towards foreign based athlete practice.

In this study, the situation of the foreign based athletes in our country and the perception created by those athletes in the sports science students were examined. As a result; investing in foreign based athletes to compete on behalf of our country in international sports organizations is seen as a serious obstacle to train athletes and sports infrastructure activities. There is a need for effective sports policies in our country that will enable better utilization of domestic human resources. In addition, foreign based athletes' success does not satisfy our people because of our national sensitivity.

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